

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES FROM JOINT BUSINESS GROUP “KUB KERIPIK GOSONG” AS ONE OF MIRACLE BY INDONESIA SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES SECTOR

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Abstract

The research was carried out at the Sei Bejangkar Plantation, Sei Balai District, Batu Bara Regency in January 2022. At Sei Bejangkar Plantation In the village, there are 11 Gosong Banana chips agroindustry in the form of households industry and started production in 2015. Then, the home industry was formed into a joint business group named KUB Keripik Gosong in 2019 and has a P-IRT certificate in 2021. After having a P-IRT certificate, KUB Keripik Gosong hopes that their profits can increase from before having a P-IRT certificate. This study aims to determine the difference in the profit of KUB Chips Gosong between the previous one and after having a P-IRT certificate. Sampling in the study used the census method with a the number of samples as many as 11 respondents. The type of data used in this study is primary data and secondary data. The data were analyzed using a two-sample paired difference test (Wilcoxon test). The results showed that the significance value (0.000) < (0.05), meaning that there is a significant difference between the average profit before and after having a P-IRT certificate at KUB Keripik Gosong. Result data The analysis shows that the average profit after having a P-IRT certificate is more than previously had a P-IRT certificate. Keywords: profit comparison, home industry, P-IRT certificate.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a developing country where most of its regional potential is the agricultural sector. As a developing country, Indonesia also has one of the characteristics of a development strategy shared by developing countries in general, namely developing the agricultural sector towards the industrial sector. The close relationship between the agricultural sector and the industrial sector has become a new paradigm in economic development which is manifested in the form of agro-industry.

The presence of agro-industry is an effort to increase added value to agricultural products, including products that are processed in the form of semi-finished and finished products produced from raw materials sourced from agricultural products. so produced from raw materials sourced from agricultural products. The development of agro-industry through the

use of raw materials derived from the potential of local agricultural products is one of the efforts to develop the agricultural sector, including through processing agricultural products into food products.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical foundation

2.1.1. Agro industry Concept

Agro industry is formed from two words, namely agricultural and industry which has the meaning of an industry whose main raw materials are sourced from agricultural products or it can also be interpreted as an industry that produces a product that is used as a means of production (input) in farming activities. Agro industry can be explained as an industrial activity by utilizing raw materials derived from agricultural products, designing, providing equipment, and services for these activities. Therefore, agro-industry includes industries that process agricultural products, industries that produce agricultural equipment and machinery (alsintan), and industries that produce agricultural inputs (fertilizers, pesticides, etc.), as well as industries that produce services in agriculture (Udayana). , 2011). According to Tama, et al (2019), agro industry is an industry that uses agricultural products as its main raw material to produce an item/product. Processing of agricultural products through agro-industry activities can increase selling prices and extend the shelf life of the products produced. Agro industry can be developed through strategies that are adapted to existing characteristics and problems. The general problem that exists in agricultural products is that they are easily damaged and do not last long. Agro industry can be developed through strategies that are adapted to existing characteristics and problems. The general problem that exists in agricultural products is that they are easily damaged and do not last long. Agro industry can be developed through strategies that are adapted to existing characteristics and problems. The general problem that exists in agricultural products is that they are easily damaged and do not last long.

2.1.2. Burnt Banana Chips

According to the National Standardization Agency (1996), banana chips are snack products made from sliced bananas which are then fried, with or without other permitted food additives. The quality requirements of banana chips have been listed in SNI 01-4135-1996, banana chips. The banana chip processing procedure consists of several series of activities, including: preparation of raw materials (bananas), equipment preparation, peeling, slicing, washing, frying, draining oil, packaging, and labeling, and storing banana chips. Burnt banana chips are chips made from crew bananas and have a savory, crunchy, and sweet taste. These charred banana chips have a blackish brown appearance resembling the color of charred chips. Therefore, these chips are called charred banana chips. These chips can be stored and last up to 3 months even without preservatives. Burnt banana chips are one of the typical foods of Batu Bara Regency whose production center is in the Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village.

2.1.3. Definition of SPP-IRT

Certificate of Household-Industrial Food Production (SPP-IRT) is a written guarantee for home-industrial food in an area given by the city government (regent/mayor). SPP-IRT is needed by SME/UMKM entrepreneurs in order to legally market the products they produce. All processed food products, whether produced domestically or imported to be marketed and packaged in retail packaging, must have a distribution permit. This is so that the food/beverage that is traded in the community can be guaranteed its safety in accordance with food safety standards and for producers to be able to market their products legally in accordance with applicable regulations in Indonesia (Komalasari et al, 2021). 8 Circulation licenses owned by producers or business actors are one of the strategies to improve the quality of the products produced. In addition to paying attention to the quality of taste, the health and safety of the products produced is also very important to note. Producers who already have a P-IRT permit will more easily penetrate the market, both self-help and modern markets (Setyowati, 2012 A distribution permit (P-IRT) can be sought on the condition that the relevant home industry must have a business license (Soejono et al, 2019).

2.1.4. Cost Concept

The term cost is also commonly referred to as an expense. Therefore, expenses are part of the costs sacrificed by the company to earn income within a certain period of time. According to Sukirno (2010) production costs are all company expenses incurred to obtain production factors and raw materials that will be used to produce a product. In analyzing production costs, it is necessary to pay attention to the time period, namely the short term and long term. Short-term production costs are classified into two, namely fixed costs (fixed costs) and costs that are always changing (variable). The concept of cost can be described as follows:

1. Total Fixed Costs (Total Fix Costs) Total fixed costs are all costs incurred to obtain production factors (inputs) whose amount is fixed or cannot be changed. Fixed costs do not depend on a firm's level of output. In fact, these costs are still incurred even though the company is not producing. Various fixed costs (no change in the short term) such as: the cost of buying machinery, the cost of building a factory, the cost of equipment and so on.
2. Total Variable Cost Total variable cost is the total cost incurred to obtain production factors (inputs) whose amount varies depending on the level of production. Total changing costs or variable costs whose amounts can vary, for example, are labor costs and raw material costs, the amount of which can change in each production process.
3. Total Cost (Total Cost) Total cost is the total cost of production incurred by the company. The total cost of production (total cost) is the sum of the total fixed costs (total fixed costs) and total variable costs (total variable costs).

2.1.5. Acceptance Concept

Revenue is the result of multiplying the production results obtained with the selling price of the product (Shinta, 2011). Meanwhile, according to Soekartawi (2006), revenue is the total

product value both for sale and for own consumption which is calculated within a certain period of time. Revenue can be calculated based on the multiplication of total production with the current price. Each of these definitions of revenue is also in line with Suratiyah's (2015) opinion which states that total revenue is the product of the total production (Y) and the selling price (Py).

2.1.6. Profit Concept

According to Sukirno (2010), the economic theory of income or profit receipts has a slightly different meaning from the definition of profit in terms of bookkeeping. In terms of the company and bookkeeping, profit is the difference in the value of money that comes from the sales obtained with the total costs sacrificed/expended. If the profit is reduced by hidden costs will produce pure profit (pure profit). This is in line with the opinion of Rahim and Hastuti (2007) who argue that profit is the result of total revenue minus the total cost.

2.1.7. Comparative Analysis

Misbahuddin (2013) suggests that comparative analysis is a comparative analysis. Comparative analysis aims to compare the similarities and differences of two or more facts and characteristics regarding the object under study based on a certain framework of thought. This comparative analysis or difference test is often referred to as a significant test. Muliawan (2014) suggests the characteristics of the comparative method, including the following:

1. represents two or more different objects,
2. Each is independent and separate,
3. Having the same pattern or certain way of working,
4. The object being compared is clear and specific,
5. Use different standards and comparison sizes of the same object.

Comparative analysis is divided into two, namely comparative between two samples and comparative k samples (comparative between more than two samples). Then, each sample comparative model is also divided into two, namely correlated or related samples and uncorrelated or independent samples (Misbahudin, 2013). According to Hasan (2010), samples are said to be correlated if the samples are not mutually exclusive (non-mutually exclusive) between one sample and another (some members of one sample are members of the other). Then, the samples are said to be independent or mutually exclusive if the samples are strictly separated from one sample to another (members of one sample are not members of the other sample).

2.2. Previous Research

Then Reza Wisnu Winata, Zainal Arifin, and Sudarti (2021), conducted a study on "Analysis of Differences in Income of Weaving Craftsmen Before and After the Modern Retail". This research is motivated by the phenomenon of the emergence of modern markets that can increase the capacity of the regional economy, but on the other hand it can threaten the

existence of small businesses, one of which includes weaving craftsmen. The purpose of this study was to determine the differences in the income of weaving craftsmen before and after the existence of modern retail in Sukarara Village, Jonggat District, Central Lombok Regency. This research was conducted using a different test method (t-test) to compare the averages of two groups that were paired with each other. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant difference between the income of weaving craftsmen before and after the existence of modern weaving retail. There was a decrease in average income of Rp.1, 775,862. Then, based on the selling price, there is no significant difference. This is due to the limited market reach and continuous control of regional cooperatives and partners, so that it does not provide a significant price difference between before and after the existence of modern retail. The difference that occurs is in business efficiency and decreased sales quantity. This causes a decrease in the income of traditional weaving craftsmen in Sukarara Village, Jonggat District, and Central Lombok Regency. Triana Nurhayati (2011), conducted research on "Analysis of the Difference in Micro Business Income Before and After Receiving Credit Assistance for the Rural Independent National Community Empowerment Program (PNPM) (Case Study of a Grocery Shop in Polokarto District, Sukoharjo Regency, Central Java Province, 2007 - 2009)". This research is motivated by the phenomenon of accelerated poverty alleviation through PNPM - Mandiri Pedesaan 13 in the form of credit aimed at developing productive economic businesses and is also expected to increase family income. The purpose of this study was to identify and analyze data relating to the provision of credit assistance from PNPM Mandiri in Rural Areas in Polokarto District, Sukoharjo Regency, and to analyze the differences in the income of micro businesses in Polokarto District before and after receiving PNPM Mandiri Rural credit assistance. This research was conducted using the paired sample t-test method (paired t-test). The results showed that there was a significant difference in the income level of micro-grocery stall entrepreneurs who received credit assistance before and after receiving credit assistance.

2.3. Hypothesis

Based on the problems and theoretical basis above, a hypothesis can be formulated, namely that there are differences in the benefits of the KUB (Joint Business Group) Keripik Gosong in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village between before and after the P-IRT (Home Industry Food) permit.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1. Location, Object and Scope of Research

This research was conducted in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village, Sei Balai District, Batu Bara Regency. The location of this research was taken intentionally (purposive sampling) which was in the Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village, Sei Balai District, Batu Bara Regency. This is because Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village is a center for the production of charred banana chips in Batu Bara Regency. Then, the village also became the place where the Keripik Gosong KUB was formed, which currently has a P-IRT permit. The object of this

research is KUB Keripik Gosong in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village, Sei Balai District, Batu Bara Regency. The scope of this research is limited to a comparative analysis of the advantages of KUB Keripik Gosong before and after the P-IRT permit in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village, Sei Balai District, Batu Bara Regency.

3.2. Data Types and Sources

The data used in this study are primary and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained directly from the Joint Business Group (KUB) Keripik Gosong. Primary data was collected through interviews with members of the Keripik Gosong KUB regarding the costs of producing charred banana chips for 3 months before the P-IRT permit was issued and 3 months after the P-IRT permit was issued. Then, secondary data is information data obtained from relevant agencies that support this research. The secondary data used in this study is data sourced from field agricultural extension workers (PPL) on duty in the Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village, namely in the form of data archives on the number of KUB Chips Gosong production for 3 months before the P-IRT permit, namely June, July,

3.3. Population and Sample

The population in this study are all business actors who are members of KUB Keripik Gosong in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village, Sei Balai District, Batu Bara Regency. In this study, the sample is the entire population, namely all business actors who are members of the KUB Keripik Gosong, totaling 11 people. The use of the entire population without having to draw a research sample as a unit of observation is called a census technique. A sample like this is called a saturated sample which is usually done if the population is relatively small or less than 30 people (Sugiyono, 2016). The sample used in this study is a related sample, meaning that the sample used is the same sample but analyzed based on two different conditions or treatments (Montolalu and Langi, 2018). The conditions referred to in this study are the conditions before and after having a P-IRT permit. So, the authors still get two sample data from the same respondent to compare, namely the profit data obtained by 11 members of the Keripik Gosong KUB for 3 months before and 3 months after having a P-IRT permit.

3.4. Data analysis method

The data analysis used in this research is quantitative descriptive analysis, which is a method that aims at solving problems that exist at the present time by collecting, compiling, explaining, analyzing and interpreting data and then drawing conclusions (Sunyoto, 2013). The data analysis technique used in this research is the two-mean difference test for two related samples (paired sample t-test). For this reason, before comparing the advantages, it is necessary to analyze costs, revenues, and profits first.

3.4.1. Cost Analysis

Before calculating the profit, first calculate the total cost. According to Sukirno (2010), the total cost can be calculated using the following formula.

$$TC = TFC + TVC$$

Information:

TC = Total Cost (Rp)

TFC = Total Fixed Cost (Rp)

TVC = Total Variable Cost (Rp)

3.4.2. Acceptance Analysis

To find out the amount of profit, you must first calculate the total revenue. According to Rahim and Hastuti (2007), the amount of revenue can be calculated using the following formula.

TR = Y. Py

Information:

TR = Total Revenue (Rp)

Y = Total Production (Rp)

Py = Product Price (Rp)

3.4.3. Profit Analysis

After calculating costs and revenues, the next step is to calculate profits. According to Rahim and Hastuti (2007), the amount of profit can be calculated using the following formula.

= TR – TC

Information:

= Burnt Chips Business Profit (Rp)

TR = Total Revenue (Rp)

TC = Total Cost (Rp)

3.4.4. Comparative Analysis

The data analysis used in this study is a paired sample t-test, namely two data measurements on the same object for certain treatments. Size before and after undergoing treatment can be measured. If a treatment has no effect, then the average difference is zero (Aisyah, 2015). Before conducting a different test, the first step that must be taken is the normality test of the data.

3.4.4.1. Data Normality Test

The normality test of the data was carried out before the data was processed based on research needs. The purpose of this normality test is to determine the distribution of the variables that will be used in the study. In research, good data to use is data that is normally distributed

3.5. Framework

3.6. Operational definition

1. The Joint Business Group (KUB) of Burnt Chips referred to in this study is a business group in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village whose members consist of 11 home industry entrepreneurs who produce charred banana chips.
2. The distribution permit or SPP-IRT (Food Production Certificate - Home Industry) referred to in this study is a distribution permit certificate for charred banana chips owned by KUB Keripik Gosong in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village.
3. The costs referred to in this study are the total costs (amount of fixed costs and variable costs) incurred by 11 members of KUB Keripik Gosong in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village to produce charred banana chips for 3 months before and 3 months after the P-IRT permit is issued. Expressed in units (Rp/month)
4. The revenue referred to in this study is the total revenue (the result of multiplying the price with the amount of burnt banana chips production) obtained by 11 members of the KUB Keripik Gosong in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village for 3 months before and 3 months after the P-IRT permit was declared. in units (Rp/month).
5. The advantage referred to in this study is the profit (reduction between total revenue and total cost) obtained by 11 members of KUB Keripik Gosong in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village for 3 months before and 3 months after the P-IRT permit is stated in units (Rp./comb).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Overview of Research Area

Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village is one of 14 villages in Sei Balai District, Batu Bara Regency, and North Sumatra Province. Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village has an area of 1,597 ha and is located above 12 meters above sea level.

Demographically, the population in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village is 2,228 people. Then socio-culturally, the Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village is dominated by 1,932 Javanese people, 223 Malays, 25 Bataks, 17 Minangs and 3 Acehnese. In terms of the livelihoods of the population, in general as many as 609 productive people working in the Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village are farmers 18.88%, employees/laborers 63.21%, traders/entrepreneurs 15.92%, civil servants 1.97% (WKPP Sei Bejangkar Plantation Agricultural Extension Program, 2021). The residents make a living as farmers with the main commodities being lowland rice, oil palm and cassava. This village is also supported by an agro-industry in the form of a home industry run by several farming families.

4.2. KUB Chips Gosong Overview

The home industry in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village which is growing rapidly is the home industry of charred banana chips. The burnt banana chip industry consists of 11 home industries, each of which has started production since 2015. In 2019, the eleven charred

banana chip industries were formed into a Joint Business Group (KUB) accompanied by Field Agricultural Extension Officers (PPL) and later called KUB Gosong Chips. Then, in 2021, KUB Keripik Gosong officially obtained a distribution permit or P-IRT (Food - Home Industry) permit for the product they produce, namely charred banana chips.

4.3. Characteristics of Respondents

4.3.1. Characteristics by Age

There are various types of classification of a person's age to say productive or not. According to Mubyarto (1992) in Sholeh, et al (2021), the unproductive age is at the age of 0-14 years, the productive age is at the age of 15-54 years and non-productive age is >54 years.

5. CLOSING

5.1. Conclusion

Based on the results of research on the comparative advantages of KUB Chips Burnt in Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village, Sei Balai District, Batu Bara Regency, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the benefits of KUB Chips Gosong before and after the P-IRT permit and the average profit before the P-IRT permit. -IRT is Rp.2,028.68/sisir, and after the P-IRT permit is Rp.2,925.78/sisir, it means that the average profit of KUB Keripik Gosong after the P-IRT permit is higher than before the P-IRT permit .

5.2. Suggestion

KUB Keripik Gosong is expected to be able to maintain the quality of the charred banana chips produced so that it can be further developed by adhering to the legality of the distribution permit or P-IRT permit that is currently owned. Then it is better if the Field Agricultural Extension Officer (PPL) who is on duty in the working area of Sei Bejangkar Plantation Village can again help KUB Keripik Gosong so that in the future their products can obtain a halal certificate from the MUI (Indonesian Ulema Council), so that the quality of these burnt banana chips can be more guaranteed and value in the eyes of consumers.

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